

Investigation of the haptic rendering of high jumping in virtual reality using a haptic foot platform.

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Abstract. A seated one-degree-of-freedom ankle platform has been designed to simulate high jumping in virtual reality. The aim is to create a more accessible and accurate virtual reality experience with realistic muscular activation. A virtual floor control system was applied to the haptic foot platform to enable haptic feedback. The experiment correlates the muscular activation of the user's Gastrocnemius Medialis and Tibialis Anterior with the jumping height of the virtual model. The results show that higher activation leads to higher virtual jumps.

Keywords: Virtual Reality · Physical Human-Robot Interaction.

1 Introduction

Previous research in Walk-in-place haptic platforms has seen promising results in simulating walking in VR [1], however, high jumping still has not been thoroughly investigated. Seated haptic VR platforms have the advantages of being more accessible to impaired users [2] and more portable [3]. However, they lack the level of feedback that walking using motion capture VR devices provides. This can be mitigated by adding haptic feedback to platforms. This research aims to investigate how a haptic platform can repeatably simulate a high jump in VR while eliciting a similar lower leg muscular activation to a real jump.

The hypothesis is that the user's muscular activation of the lower leg is directly proportional to the maximum jump height of the virtual robot.

2 Design and Methods

A one-degree foot platform has been developed using the HRX-1 haptic robotic platform³ with a pulley transmission system with a 20:1 ratio as shown in Fig.1. The platform's built-in motor renders a virtual floor. A dynamic virtual reality model of a humanoid leg was created in Unity. Two surface EMG probes are placed on the user's leg to monitor the muscular activation. A single user (25 years, male) tested the platform. The user was instructed to jump at three different heights.

The virtual jumping algorithm converts the user's shaft position to the robot's crouching extent. When in jumping mode, the virtual floor tracks the user's foot. Once the user

³ HRX-1 Robot at <https://humanrobotix.co.uk>

is satisfied with the robot's crouching extent, they can extend their foot on the virtual floor, the opposing torque generated by the floor is directly converted to torque applied to the virtual robot's ankle joint with a scaling factor.

Fig. 1. a) Diagram of the foot platform for interacting with the virtual environment. The range of motion is 83 degrees and it is mounted sideways. Image illustrating the platform used with the surface EMG sensors on the user's leg. b) Screen Capture of the virtual reality environment, showing the robot's virtual jumping in stages. The stages consist of 1) Crouching (affected by the user's foot angle), 2) Jumping (affected by the user's force on the haptic virtual floor), and, 3) Landing. These states emerge from the dynamic model simulation in Unity.

3 Results

The results, shown in Fig. 2, give promising evidence that the platform can accurately render a higher virtual high jump. The EMG activation has been bandpass filtered (40-400Hz), notch filtered (50Hz), root-mean-squared and the envelope acquired using a moving average filter.

During the standing phase, the robot is not moving and the EMG activation is minimal. During the crouching phase, the robot's head height decreases as the Tibialis Anterior (TA) activates. As the user is dorsiflexing the ankle, the TA activation reaches peak activation. To initiate virtual jumping, the Gastrocnemius Medialis (GM) activates and reaches a peak when the robot's vertical velocity (slope of the red graph) is the highest. In the air phase, both the TA and GM stay active, however, this may not be the case in real jumps. This can be explained by the fact that the platform's virtual floor deactivates, causing the user to instinctively counteract the platform's inertia and weight from overextending the foot. This effect may be mitigated by adding inertia and gravity compensation to the platform's control system. During the landing phase, the robot bounces back while absorbing the collision's impact, and the EMG activation returns to the initial conditions.

Despite the muscular activation not being fully realistic, the results also show a clear pattern of increasing EMG activation resulting in higher jump heights. These results

support the hypothesis that the platform can proportionally translate muscular effort into height during a virtual jump. However, further research is needed to evaluate the repeatability across multiple users to provide conclusive results.

Fig. 2. Preliminary results correlating EMG activation of Tibialis Anterior (Blue), Gastrocnemius Medialis (Purple), and robot height (red).

4 Future Work

Due to the promising single-user results, we are planning an experiment with multiple participants to collect statistically significant data. A similar experimental method will be employed. Additionally, the muscular activation of real jumping will be compared to the activation using the platform.

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References

1. Boletsis, C.: The new era of virtual reality locomotion: A systematic literature review of techniques and a proposed typology. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction* **1**(4) (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti1040024>, <https://www.mdpi.com/2414-4088/1/4/24>
2. Nilsson, N.C., Serafin, S., Steinicke, F., Nordahl, R.: Natural walking in virtual reality: A review. *Comput. Entertain.* **16**(2) (4) 2018). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3180658>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3180658>
3. Otaran, A., Farkhatdinov, I.: Haptic ankle platform for interactive walking in virtual reality. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* **28**(12), 3974–3985 (2022)